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INFLUENCE OF GRAPE SEED POWDER ON ANTHOCYANIN TRANSFORMATION PROCESS DURING AGING OF RED DRY WINE MADE FROM OJALESHI GRAPE VARIETY

Annotation. Wine is one of the most widely used alcoholic products worldwide and enjoys great popularity, although it is relatively perishable unlike other alcoholic beverages, which is manifested by the appearance of various diseases, diseases or vices in wine.

The beauty of red wine lies in its color, which in the main cases is characterized by ruby (of varying intensity), however, during the production and storage of wine, the color can change and the ruby color of the wine becomes yellowish brown, which is definitely unacceptable.

Keywords: red wine, production, dry wine

At all stages of the production and storage of red wine, tannins play an important role. They are involved in oxidation-reduction processes, together with protein substances, they produce tanates that promote wine purification, participate in the process of preserving the color of old wine.

With the aging of wine, anthocyanins, which determine the coloration of red wine, hydrolyze, form volatile glycosides, oxidize and precipitate, which leads to a decrease and change in the intensity of red wine color.

Research objective

The aim of our research was to prepare a powder from grape seed, by processing it, which found application in winemaking, in particular in the process of wine processing, and to study its impact on wine quality and aging process.

Main part

In the 2017 season, ojaleshi grapes were harvested by hand, after proper inspection, the Claret was removed and prepared for fermentation. The fermentation process took place in accordance with all the rules, according to the classical method of producing red wine. fermentation proceeded at 22-26 IU C for 15 days.

The resulting wine material was separated from the leek and divided into two parts. one part (sample I) was directly placed in a stainless metal reservoir, and the other part (sample II) was treated with a pod powder obtained from the same grape.

To obtain the pod powder, we dried and ground the pod distinguished from the fermented residues of the same grapes. We introduced the resulting powder into the wine and set it down, after which filtration took place.

To create equal conditions, we filtered sample I to the same conditions as sample I to ii.

After that, both samples were treated with cold, and after processing, both samples under the same conditions were poured into bottles and placed for aging. We checked each bottle once a year.

Consequences and their judgment

Wine aging (both samples) took place in bottles, under the same conditions. After pouring wine into bottles every year (in november of each year), we tested the color by visual inspection method. Wine color characteristics by years are presented in the table 1.

Table 1

Test and control wine color characteristics by years

<i>Year</i>	<i>Sample I</i>	<i>Sample II</i>
2016	Dark ruby	Dark ruby
2017	Dark ruby	Dark ruby
2018	Dark ruby	Dark ruby
2019	Dark ruby, with a brown tint	Dark ruby
2020	Brownish, with an orange tint	Dark ruby, with a brown tint
2021	Brown	Dark ruby, with a brown tint

As can be seen from the table, wine that was not treated with Pod powder (sample II) retained a dark ruby color for two years, and after two years its color slowly changed and after five years it acquired a brown hue. as for the wine, which we processed with grape Seed Powder, the color retained for three years, and after three years the dynamics of color change was rather slow.

Based on the foregoing, it can be said that the processing of wine with powder made from grape seed positively affects the quality of wine during the aging process, however, additional studies and observations are needed on the transformation of anthocyanins in wine, powder dosage and other processing conditions.

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